

LASER ABLATION ASSISTED ADHESIVE BONDING OF AUTOMOTIVE STRUCTURAL COMPOSITES

*C. DAVID WARREN, FELIX L. PAULAUSKAS and RAY G. BOEMAN
Oak Ridge National Laboratory, P.O. Box 2009, Oak Ridge, TN 37831-8039*

Keywords : adhesive bonding, laser, automotive applications, joining

In the past few years, Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) has been involved in a national initiative to conduct research aimed at promoting the use of lighter weight materials in automotive structures for the purpose of increasing fuel efficiency and reducing environmental pollutant emissions. A key component of this initiative is the joining of non-ferrous materials specifically employing adhesive bonding. Unfortunately, the implementation of adhesives on the manufacturing plant floor suffers from a significant economical obstacle. Adherends joined with structural adhesives often require extensive surface preparation procedures to maximize joint integrity. These additional production steps result in elevated assembly time and costs. In order to make the use of adhesives for primary composite structures a reality in high production rate, consumer goods industries, technologies for rapid surface preparation of the adherends must be discovered, developed and deployed. The goal of this project is to provide one enabling technology, adhesive bonding, which will allow for the use of fiber reinforced polymer composites. Specifically, laser ablation is evaluated to determine its effectiveness as a surface preparation method for high production rate industries.

This process is easily automated and the laser can be used to ablate only the areas to be bonded leaving the remainder of a composite structure unaffected. This technology is expected to remove mold releases, surface impurities and the resin rich composite surface.

Laser ablation has been evaluated as a surface pretreatment prior to adhesive bonding. In prior experimental work it was demonstrated that when adhesively bonded, composite, single lap shear samples fail, the fracture often occurs at either the adhesive/adherend interface or in the resin rich sub-surface layer of the composite. These two areas represent the weakest portion of the joint. Laser ablation pretreatment generates areas where the resin on the composite surface is selectively removed leaving behind exposed reinforcing fibers which are the load bearing members of the composite. In a subsequent adhesive bonding operation, this allows portions of the fibers to be encapsulated in the adhesive while other portions of the fiber remain in the composite resin. This type of pretreatment permits fibers to bridge and reinforce the interface between adhesive and adherend. Secondary benefits are the removal of surface contaminants by pyrolysis which adds to the resulting joint strength. Microscopic observation of laser ablated surfaces indicates a prominent, fiber rich area.

Results of the mechanical evaluation indicated that the ultimate tensile strength for laser ablated samples was slightly lower than for similar, conventionally prepared specimens.

"The submitted manuscript has been authored by a contractor of the U.S. Government under contract No. DE-AC05-96OR22464. Accordingly, the U.S. Government retains a nonexclusive, royalty-free license to publish or reproduce the published form of this contribution, or allow others to do so, for U.S. Government purposes." Research was performed at Oak Ridge National Laboratory and sponsored by the U.S. Department of Energy under contract DE-AC05-96OR22464 with Lockheed Martin Energy Research Corp.